

MATRIX SOLIDIFICATION AND SEGREGATION EFFECTS IN FIBRE REINFORCED METALS

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INTRODUCTION.

The current revival of interest in fibre reinforced metals (FRM) has stemmed from the rapid expansion of commercially available ceramic fibres that can be incorporated in light alloys to produce components of high specific stiffness and strength. Many workers have explored the stability of various ceramic fibres in molten aluminium as well as the effects that alloying elements may have on the overall fibre/matrix reactivity. These studies have particular relevance to FRM manufacturing techniques such as liquid metal infiltration (LMI). However, another important factor which must be taken into account concerns the manner in which impurities as well as alloying elements in the metal may segregate within the microstructure of the composite during the solidification process.

The present paper discusses some problems which can arise when using a LMI process to manufacture FRM components. The composite microstructures, which are characteristic of a casting-type process, contain a complex series of interfaces between the major components of the composite (fibre and matrix). These interfaces may be further complicated by chemical reaction between alloy and fibre. Where, as commonly occurs, the interfacial phases are brittle. They can give rise to poor mechanical properties of the composite.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION.

Figure 1 illustrates schematically the main factors which need to be considered for successful application of LMI techniques to the manufacture of FRM components. We shall use this representation as a basis for discussion, focusing attention on some of the chemical effects and their consequences as experienced in our research on fibre-reinforced metals.

The basic LMI fabrication method is akin to casting and gives rise to a similar microstructure whereby solidification of a hypo-eutectic matrix alloy initiates within the interfibre regions^{1,2}. Solute is rejected ahead of the melt front to impinge on the fibre network and as a result, alloying elements and impurities tend to segregate at the fibre/matrix interface. Figure 2 is a typical as-cast microstructure of an aluminium alloy reinforced with Nicalon fibres showing a second phase segregated at the fibre/matrix interface. Use of x-ray microanalysis has identified the constituent as FeAl_6 , the iron impurity being introduced into the molten metal during fabrication of the composite.

Another source of composite contamination may be caused by the binder used to facilitate fibre preform handling as, for example, silicate binders in aluminium alloys reinforced with Saffil fibres³. Figure 3 shows a reaction between a molten magnesium matrix and the silicate glass weft used in a Nicalon fibre cloth. Copious amounts of a second phase, identified as Mg_2Si , can be seen throughout the composite microstructure and these intermetallics have been shown to possess brittle characteristics in previous work¹.

The manner in which such second phases may influence the tensile properties of the composite is complex and the problem has been studied by several workers. Ochiai et al ⁴ proposed a simple model to describe fibre strength based upon the idea that a reaction layer failed at a lower strain than the associated fibre and that it acted as a Griffith type crack which led to a reduction in strength, σ_f , of the fibre:

$$\sigma_f \approx [E_f G_c^* / \pi c]^{1/2}, \quad (1)$$

where E_f is the fibre elastic modulus, G_c^* is the critical strain energy release rate for the fibre and c is the reaction layer width. This expression can then be used to predict composite strength as a function of reaction layer width by applying the rule of mixtures as follows:

$$\sigma_c = V_f \cdot \sigma_f + (1 - V_f) \cdot \sigma_m, \quad (2)$$

where σ_c , σ_m are the composite and matrix tensile strengths and V_f is the fibre volume fraction. Hunt ⁵ has applied this type of model to fibre-matrix reaction zones in alumina-fibre reinforced Al-Li alloys, produced via an LMI technique, and found a reasonable correlation between theoretical and experimental composite strengths.

Here we have calculated composite strengths using equations (1) and (2) for an aluminium alloy reinforced with 25% V_f Safimax fibre, taking $G_c^* = 28 \text{ Jm}^{-2}$. The data are shown as a smooth curve in figure 4a. There must be a cut-off at small values of c , since the composite strength would otherwise rise to infinity. This limiting value of σ_c may be predicted using Zweben's statistical failure criterion ⁶, which gives the fibre strength, based upon Weibull statistics, as

$$\sigma_f = \sigma_0 \cdot [4 \cdot N \cdot l \cdot \delta (k^m - 1)]^{-1/2m}, \quad (3)$$

k is taken as 1.146 for a square array of fibres, l is the fibre gauge length, N is the number of fibres, σ_0 is the difference between the upper and lower fibre strength and m is the Weibull modulus; δ is termed the "ineffective fibre length" and has been expressed as

$$\delta = D \cdot [(V_f^{-1/2} - 1) \cdot E_f / 2G_m]^{1/2}, \quad (4)$$

where D is the fibre diameter and G_m is the matrix shear modulus. Insertion of values calculated from equations (3) and (4) into equation (2) gives the limiting value for the composite strength. This is shown as a horizontal broken line in figure 4 and its intersection with the curve provides the critical value for the width of intermetallic for this system; in this case the width is $\approx 0.7 \mu\text{m}$. Figure 4b illustrates a similar series of calculated data for a 50% V_f composite. Again the critical value for the composite strength has been predicted using equations (2), (3) and (4). The interesting point emerges that these calculations suggest the critical width of intermetallic is slightly greater for the higher volume fraction of fibre.

Bend test data obtained on a number of composite systems are given in table 1. Also included are strength values calculated using equation (2). In every case the experimentally measured value is less than the value calculated using the rule of mixtures. Also in every case, brittle intermetallic phases have segregated to the fibre matrix interface, although they do not produce the continuous layers as required by the above

theory. Nevertheless, where extensive intermetallic formation occurs, as in figure 3 for example, a very low composite strength is achieved. The experimentally measured value for this composite (magnesium reinforced with Nicalon) was 225 ± 10 MPa, only 18% of the calculated value. There is some measure of agreement between microstructure and strength in that the intermetallic width equates with the fibre separation of $\approx 10 \mu\text{m}$ and this is in accord with predicted strengths. In contrast, the width of the intermetallic seen in figure 2 is somewhat less and the strength achieved for one of the aluminium alloys reinforced with Nicalon, 515 ± 55 MPa, is a much higher percentage (60 %) of the calculated value.

As an additional point, the presence of intermetallics will influence such physical effects as thermal stresses, see figure 1. Indeed, the present work provides evidence for the deleterious behaviour of phases segregated to the fibre/matrix interface and also indicates the potential benefits on composite properties if they can be avoided.

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Composite system	Vf %	Strength, MPa		A/B
		Expt. (A)	Calc. (B)	%
Safimax/Al	20	381±38	480	79
Nicalon/Al	16	369±74	484	78
Nicalon/Al	32	516±55	868	60
Nicalon/Mg	48	225±10	1252	18
Safimax/Mg	30	335±58	670	50

Table 1 Flexure test results for various fibre reinforced metals.

Fig. 1 Factors relevant to the manufacture of FRMs, with particular reference to a liquid metal infiltration route.

I—I 50 μ m

Fig. 2 Aluminium alloy reinforced with Nicalon fibre showing FeAl_6 intermetallic, optical micrograph.

I—I 10 μ m

Fig. 3 Magnesium alloy reinforced with Nicalon fibre showing Mg_2Si intermetallic, optical micrograph.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 4 Effect of intermetallic width on the tensile strength of Safimax/aluminium composite a) 25% V_f , b) 50% V_f

6. Ceramic Matrix Composites

